

The Role of Mathematics in Society

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Abstract: just as the subjects studied during a person's life are much needed, mathematics is the most necessary of these subjects. The place of mathematics for any expenditure is kata. Any actions of our society are carried out on the basis of the science of mathematics. The article discusses these.

Keywords: pedagogy, word date, methodical method, mathematics, basic task.

Upbringing is aimed at a specific goal, and includes a number of educational activities specially prepared by society, carried out by people, teachers or educators, various types of training, specially conducted. In addition to educating the child, education should be established. Education is one of the methods aimed at mastering the knowledge, skills and abilities of children, developing their mental strength, abilities for the acquisition of general education and the means of general education. As the child receives education, he sharpens his mental activity, gradually begins to step into a social society, becomes aware of his self, begins to set himself various goals. In the development of a child's personality with a close connection of education and upbringing, upbringing also has a leading place, and thanks to upbringing, it is possible to draw the conclusion that it is able to develop comprehensively under the influence of lineage, family environment, social environment. That is, in the process of educating the student, attention should also be paid to their psyche. Because, without knowing the child, knowledge, skills, qualifications cannot be formed in him.

Mathematics is a science that can reveal the innovative features of the educational process as well as about systematic activities aimed at a specific goal in the development of the intellectual activity of the child. The main task of mathematics is to cultivate the mental consciousness of the child to determine his place in the life of society. Mathematics is the main criterion that shapes the social life of a student as a competent person, connecting with pedagogy. All the positive results that the teacher must achieve in his activities in the field of educational education are visible in the correct Organization of free communication with students. It is necessary that the teacher, on the basis of the infinite power of the word art, has an educational impact on students, curiously organizes each lesson. The skill of the teacher is determined by the moral decency and erudition of the disciples he brought up, in a word, by their spirituality. This process is manifested through the science of pedagogy, that is, through pedagogical influence, in language. Pedagogical influence is the reason for the formation and development of pedagogical phenomena. For example, the role of group members in the influence of Group communities, or the emergence of positive activity in a student under the influence of a teacher. The liberalization of the economy in our republic and the further deepening of reforms in this area also strengthened the requirements for obtaining knowledge, studying the mysteries of mathematics. This, in turn, requires not only the training of mathematicians with the right decision-making skills, but also the training of educators who train them.

To teach mathematical subjects to young people, the teacher himself is required to be well versed in these subjects, to be able to skillfully apply teaching methods. At the same time, it will be necessary to have a deep knowledge of pedagogy, psychology and other sciences. The main goal in the training of personnel is to develop the intellectual abilities of students, in addition to mastering the necessary knowledge, to create in them an independent selection and decision-making skill. The mathematics lesson will increase the mental load, as well as make the student think that the material being passed should increase activity and interest in the lesson in the entire course process. Therefore, new active teaching is taught to express methods and methodical methods, the ability to activate the opinion of students, to acquire them independent knowledge. Interest in mathematics depends on the high level of the teaching method and how much it builds the teaching work. In the lesson, it is necessary to be attentive to the fact that each student works actively and with pleasure, and to deepen his interest in acquiring knowledge, using the desire for knowledge as a starting point for its emergence and development. This is especially important for adolescents, when they are formed again, it is only necessary to determine their constant interests and interest in this or that discipline. At this time, criticism of aspects of mathematics that are engaging should be quick.

In addition to the direct practical implementation of mathematics, it is necessary to emphasize that the younger generation has a special place in the upbringing of mature people who have developed in every way. Analytical reasoning, logical observation, spatial imagination, abstract thinking are necessary abilities for all areas of human activity, which are formed and deepened in the process of studying mathematics.

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